

GAME TECHNOLOGY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL SCHOOLS

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ANNOTATSIYA

Teachers from all over the world are looking for ways to improve the effectiveness of teaching. One of the most important solutions to this problem is the development and implementation of new pedagogical technologies. The technological approach to teaching provides for precise instrumental management of the educational process and guaranteed success of the set educational goals.

Everyone knows that for the development of a sense of rhythm, tact, musical ear and memory in children, it is necessary to closely acquaint them with musical games from an early age. Play, along with work and learning, is one of the main types of human activity, an amazing phenomenon of our existence. By definition, play is a type of activity under conditions of situations aimed at recreating and assimilating social experience, in which self-management of behavior develops and improves. The value of the game cannot be exhausted and appreciated by the entertainment-reactive possibilities. This is where her phenomenon is contained, which is entertainment, rest, she is able to develop into training, into a model of education.

The game as a method of teaching and upbringing, transferring the experience of older generations to younger people has been used since antiquity. The game is widely used in folk pedagogy, in preschool and out-of-school institutions. In a modern school, which relies on the activation and intensification of the educational process, play activity is used in the following cases: as independent technologies for mastering a concept, topic and even a section of a subject; as elements (sometimes quite essential) of a broader technology; as a technology of a lesson (lesson) or fragment; - as a technology of extracurricular work.

"The concept of" play pedagogical technologies "includes a fairly extensive group of methods and techniques for organizing the pedagogical process in the form of various pedagogical games." Pedagogical play, in contrast to ordinary games, has an essential feature - a clearly defined goal of teaching and the corresponding pedagogical results that can be substantiated, are highlighted in an explicit form and are characterized by educational and cognitive orientation. "Games are a specially organized activity that requires the exertion of emotional and mental strength" - M.F. Stronin. The game always involves making a decision, what to do? What to say? The solution of these questions sharpens the thinking activity of the players. For children, play is, first of all, an exciting activity. In the game, everyone is equal. It is feasible even for the weakest students. The feeling of equality, joy - all this gives the children the opportunity to overcome the shyness that prevents them from having a beneficial effect on the learning results. The game is a small situation, the construction of which resembles a chromatic work with its own plot, conflict and characters. In the course of the game, the situation is played out several times and each time in a new version. But at the same time, the situation of the game is a situation of real life. Despite the clear conditions of the game, there is always an element of surprise in it. Hearing an unexpected question, the child begins to think about how to answer it. Therefore, the game is characterized by spontaneity of speech. Speech communication, which includes not only one's own speech, such as gesture, facial expressions, has a purposefulness and is mandatory. In human

practice, play activity performs the following *Functions*:

Entertaining (this is the main function of the game - to entertain, please, inspire, arouse interest);

Communicative: mastering the dialectics of communication;

Self-realization in the game as a testing ground for human practice;

Diagnostic: identifying deviations from normal behavior;

Correction function: making positive changes in the structure of personality indicators;

Interethnic communication: assimilation of social and cultural values common to all people;

Socialization: inclusion in the system of social relations, the assimilation of the norms of human community. Most games have four main features. Free developmental activity, undertaken only at the request of the child, for the pleasure of the process of activity itself, and not only from the result. Creative, largely improvisational. This activity is very active. Emotional elevation of activity, rivalry, competitiveness, competition, attraction, etc. (sensual nature of the game, "emotional stress");

The presence of direct or indirect rules. Reflective game content.

The structure of the game as an activity organically includes goal-setting, planning, goal realization, as well as the analysis of the results in which a person fully realizes himself as a subject. Motivation of play activity is provided by its voluntariness, choice opportunities and elements of competition, satisfaction of the need for self-affirmation, self-realization.

The structure of the game as a process includes:

Roles taken on by the players;

Play actions as a means of realizing these roles;

Game use of objects, i.e. replacement of real things with play, conventional;

Real relationships between the players;

Plot (content is an area of reality, conventionally reproduced in the game. The

value of the game cannot be exhausted and appreciated by the entertainment and

recreational opportunities. This is its phenomenon, that being entertainment,

rest, it can develop into training. Play in learning is a vivid example of two planning,

when the pedagogical goal is hidden and appears in a veiled form. Analysis of the

literature on the use of play in learning shows that play is a multifunctional

phenomenon. It is difficult to overestimate the educational value of the game, its all-

round influence on the child. The game helps to unite the children's team, timid and

shy ones are involved in active activities and this contributes to the self-affirmation of

everyone in the team. Conscious discipline, hard work, mutual assistance,

independence are brought up in games.

In the classroom, the game form of classes is created with the help of game techniques and situations, which act as a means of encouraging students to learning activities.

The implementation of game techniques and situations in the lesson form of classes occurs in the following main directions: a didactic goal is set for students in the form of a game task; educational activity is subject to the rules of the game; the educational material is used as its means, the element of competition is introduced into the educational activity, which

translates the didactic task into the game one; the successful completion of the didactic task is associated with the game result.

The game activity program consists of a set of educational games, which, with all their diversity, have one common idea. Each game is a set of tasks. Tasks are given to the child in various forms - in the form of a model, a flat isometric drawing, a drawing, oral or written instruction - and thus acquaint him with different ways of transmitting information. Tasks can be very diverse: easy - accessible to kids and difficult - unbearable for an adult. Therefore, tasks can develop a child, constantly complicating tasks. This allows the child to move forward and improve on their own.

In developing games, it was possible to combine one of the basic principles of teaching from simple to complex with a very important principle of teaching creative activity independently according to one's abilities. This allows you to solve several problems at once related to the development of creative abilities:

Developmental games can nourish creativity from an early age;

Tasks are always ahead of the development of abilities;

Rising independently, reaching a certain level, the child develops most successfully. All educational games are diverse in content, but create an atmosphere of ease and joy. In the game model of the educational process, a problem situation is created through the introduction of a game situation.

The basis of the activity is game modeling, part of the students' activity takes place in a conditionally game plan.

The results of the game are twofold - both game and educational and cognitive results. The didactic function of the game is realized through the discussion of the game action, the analysis of the correlation of the game situation as a modeling one, its correlation with reality.

The most important role belongs to the discussion, in which students jointly analyze the results of the game, the relationship between the game model and reality. The effectiveness of didactic games depends on:

Their systematic use the purposefulness of the program of games in combination with the usual didactic exercises. Game technology is built as a holistic education that covers a certain part of the educational process and is united by a common content, plot, character. The game plot develops in parallel with the main content of the training, helps to activate the educational process, to master the educational elements. Compilation of gaming technologies from individual games and elements is the concern of every primary school teacher. Thus, much depends on the teacher's understanding of the functions and classification of pedagogical games. Gaming technologies have been used in teaching since time immemorial. They are now more commonly used in primary education. In secondary and high school, they rarely turn to gaming technologies. Games can be used when getting to know each other in the initial stages of learning; can be combined with various psychological and pedagogical trainings for the development of communication. They can also be used directly in the learning process.

CONCLUSION

Play is a powerful stimulus for learning; it is a varied and powerful motivation for learning. In the game, the psychological processes of the participants in the game activity are activated: attention, memorization, interest, perception and thinking. Unique feature of the game. It consists in the fact that it allows you to expand the boundaries of a child's own life, to imagine what he did not see, to imagine from someone else's story what was not in his direct experience.

The game is emotional by its nature and experience is capable of reviving even the most dry information, making it vivid and memorable. In the game, it is possible to involve everyone in active work; this form of lesson opposes passive listening and reading. In the process of playing, an intellectually passive child will freely perform such a volume of work that is completely inaccessible to him in a normal educational situation.

The game allows you to use for educational purposes the energy that schoolchildren spend on "underground" play activities.

The concept of "play pedagogical technologies" includes a fairly extensive group of methods and techniques for organizing the pedagogical process in the form of various pedagogical games.

Unlike games in general, pedagogical play has an essential feature - a clearly defined goal of teaching and the corresponding pedagogical results that can be substantiated, singled out in an explicit form and are characterized by an educational and cognitive orientation.

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